

BULLYING: EDUCATIONAL KEYS TO DIAGNOSTIC AND INTERVENTION PROCEDURES

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Abstract: Bullying is a form of peer violence in which one or more students constantly and repeatedly harass and assault one or more classmates, who are unable to defend themselves effectively and are generally in a disadvantaged or inferior position. Bullying stems from strong frustration coupled with poor restraint and repression of aggressive responses learned during the early socialization process. However, frustration may not lead to violence, but rather to problem avoidance, indifference and depression. The purpose of this study is to examine educational intervention programs to prevent bullying situations. This aspect is a fundamental element in managing and designing programs or educational actions within the framework of a school tutorial action plan. To this end, this work will be considered from a approach of paradigmatic and methodological complementarily, although prioritizing actions of psychology individual level to continue working with socio-cultural approaches at the group level.

Keywords: school bullying, socio-educational intervention, educational support, educational actions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Bullying is a type of violence by one student or group of students (bully/s) towards another student (harassed), which is fundamentally characterized by this situation in itself (Jalón and Diaz-Aguado, 2006; Garaigordobil and Oñederra, 2010; Ortega and Mora-Merchán, 2008; Nickerson, 2019). If we delve deeper into this term, the main features that characterize this type of violence are, according to the guidelines set forth by García and Ascensio (2015), the following:

1. It causes disturbances in the socialization process of the students.
2. This type of aggression in turn provokes alternations in the bully, since he/she may permanently assume this role during his/her life, thus negatively affecting the different areas of his/her life.
3. Difficult to detect.
4. It can manifest itself in different forms and degrees: physical, psychological, verbal, direct, indirect violence...
5. Durable in time.
6. It is conscious and intentional
7. It is usually linked to the presence of a trait in the victim that makes him/her different from the group and somehow places him/her in an inferior position in front of it

As we can appreciate from the table below, there are different forms of bullying that can be classified in this way:

TABLE 1: DIFFERENT FORMS OF BULLYING

	Direct	Indirect
Physical level	-Pushing -Pasting -Threatening with weapons	-Stealing objects -Breaking up objects -Hide objects
Verbal level	-Insult -Mock -Putting nicknames	-Speaking ill of that person -Spreading false rumors
Social exclusion	-Exclude from the group -Not allowed to participate	-Ignore

Source: Data Adapted from i Caralt and Escudé, 2006

For this reason, it is important to highlight four fundamental aspects (Suckling 2006):

1. Repetition of episodes
2. Intentionality
3. Superimposition of the aggressor on the victim
4. Negative consequences for the whole environment

On the other hand, Castillo-Pulido (2011) states that it is necessary to mention and deal with the roles that arise in a harassment situation. In this case they will be classified as: aggressor, victim and spectators.

Aggressor

Aggressor students are materialized in all shapes and sizes, some are large and strong while others are short and thin. Others are popular young people with lots of friends and good school grades. But if we examine their minds, we find something that every aggressor has in common, insecurity (Rech 2013). Against what may have appeared and even imagined by much of public opinion, the aggressor or harasser does have sufficient social skills to perpetrate his/her acts and execute them (Estévez 2008; Hazler and Carney 2000). In this sense, in a high percentage of cases he enjoys powers of persuasion, psychological manipulation, a charismatic personality, strong convictions and ingrained beliefs, which he does not hesitate to use, if necessary, to justify his/her actions ... (Schmidt and McAdams 2007)

In most cases they seek the support of the group. There are two types of aggressor:

- * Predominantly dominant, with antisocial traits and proactive aggression
- * Predominantly anxious, with low self-esteem, high level of anxiety and reactive aggression.

Aggressors of anxious behaviour often have deficits in processing social information and sometimes show a tendency to over-attribute hostility to others. This results in the systematic rejection of their peers (i Caralt and Escudé 2006)

Victim

Victims of bullying are mostly passive subjects with shy, sensitive, and lonely personalities. They show insecurity in themselves and have low self-esteem. In extreme cases, individuals may even display suicidal thoughts (Cava 2011). The stalker's violent behavior towards the stalker makes the stalker less and less confident in solving the problem. There is a sub-group of victims, those called by Olweus (2007) as "the provocative victims or stalker-victims", who present patterns of restlessness and aggressive reactions.

Olweus defines them by the following characteristics:

"These students often have trouble concentrating and may have difficulty reading and writing. They behave in ways that can cause irritation and tension around them. Some of these students may be hyperactive. It is not uncommon for their attitude to be provocative in front of many of the other students, resulting in negative reactions from a large part of the student body, but from the entire class. The dynamics of the bully/victim problem within a class with provocative victims differs, in part, from the problems of a class with passive victims" (Olweus 2007, p. 8)

Spectators

In some occasions they observe without intervening but most of the time they join this action. Ortega and Mora- Merchán (2008) argue that the reason for this may be:

1. Social contagion
2. Fear of harassment for not following the group.

It is necessary and appropriate to point out that this type of violence has negative consequences, which produce long-term consequences for victims and harassers. These aggressive and discriminatory behaviors are very serious, and even more so when they occur at an early age, since they can leave lifelong consequences for both the victim and the aggressor (Carozo 2015).

TABLE 2: CHARACTERISTICS OF THE AGENTS INVOLVED IN BULLYING

In the victims...	Stress	Depression	Anxiety	Flashback
	Suicidal ideas	Deterioration of self-esteem	Somatizations	Image self- denial
In the aggressors...	Generalization of their behavior to establish social bonds	Increase in the problems that led them to abuse their strength	Decrease in the capacity for moral understanding and empathy	Identification with the domain-submission model behind the harassment
	Risk of further use of violence in the same and other contexts in the future	Preliminary to criminal behaviour		
In the audience...	Reinforcement for individualistic and selfish positions	Lack of sensitivity to cases of violence	Positive assessment of aggressive behaviour	Apathy
	Insolidarity with regard to the problems of others	Risk of being a protagonist of violence in the future		

Source: Information adapted from the Subdirectorate General for Educational Inspection, Ministry of Education and Employment (Spain), 2007.

With regard to the types of bullying, José Antonio Oñederra (2008) classifies them in this way:

- * Physical: Direct: against the body. Hitting, pushing...; Indirect: against property. Stealing, breaking...
- * Verbal: insults, mocking, nicknames, slander... These are the most frequent.
- * Psychological: they undermine self-esteem and foster insecurity and fear. The psychological component is found in all forms of abuse.
- * Social: they isolate the individual from the group.

At the same time, new forms of bullying are taking place:

- * Cyberbullying, which is characterized by the use of new information and communication technologies, such as the Internet and mobile phones, to mistreat the harassed. It is a form of indirect and anonymous harassment (Garaigordobil, 2015).
- * Happy slapping : The recordings of brutal physical aggressions or humiliations that are broadcast via mobile phone or internet is called (Palasinski, 2012).
- * Dating violence: harassment between couples of teenagers, where emotional blackmail prevails It is considered the antechamber of gender-based violence (Marganski and Melander 2018).

As for the different theories that support this type of violence, we can find them:

TABLE 3: THEORIES ON SCHOOL VIOLENCE

Contextual or ecological	Aggressive behaviour is the result of the complex interaction between the child's characteristics and other factors arising from the different contexts and prevailing values in which he or she lives
Social skills	It is the result of a deficit of appropriate social skills, which are different in aggressors and victims. Offenders score higher than victims on social skills tests.
Sociological	The cause lies in the social facts that precede it and not in individual states of consciousness.
From the mind	It refers to the ability of people to attribute mental states to themselves or others in order to explain and predict behavior. Aggressors require a high degree of elaboration in their mental theories, as they have to make the victim feel the aggression (direct attack or rejection) while the viewers approve of it.
Behaviorist	This is the result of learning by imitating violent models. This occurs to the extent that the subject identifies with the model according to their scale of anger and rage or their level of resistance by being anxious and prone to anger. In addition, the observation of a model who is rewarded for his violent behaviour decreases one's own usual inhibition to act in the same way.
Biochemistry	Biochemical, neuronal and hormonal processes are fundamental in aggressive behaviour; these are triggered by a series of internal biochemical processes in which hormones play a decisive role
Psychoanalytic	The individual carries within himself sufficient energy to destroy his fellow man and himself (death drive).
Frustration-aggression	Aggressive behavior is the result of not meeting basic needs, as well as uncontrolled frustration over desires or non-basic needs.
Mimetics	Desire is at the base of aggressive relationships and is of a mimetic nature, that is, imitating the desire of another, copying the desire of another for an object, which can be real (money, a person...) or metaphysical (prestige, honour, flag... or nothing)
Classic of pain	Pain, physical or psychic, is in itself sufficient to activate aggressive behavior; there is a direct relationship between the intensity of the stimulus (pain) and the response (aggression).
Cathartica	Catharsis is the sudden expression of repressed feelings, affections... whose release is necessary to maintain the proper state of relaxation, otherwise aggressive behaviors will explode.
Ethology of Aggression	It includes all the currents of knowledge that consider aggression as an innate, impulsive behaviour, relegated to an unconscious, almost physiological level. Due to the spontaneity of violent behavior there is no pleasure associated with it. Ethologists and psychoanalysts are included in this theoretical trend.
Social construction	Social relations are formed and maintained on the basis of conflicts of interest, but it is when mediating instruments, strategies and peaceful conflict resolution procedures fail that aggressive or violent behaviour occurs.

Source: Information adapted from Oñederra, 2008

Finally, Oñederra (2008, p. 18-19) states that bullying has harmful consequences for the bullied, as well as for the bully and the spectator.

1. Poor academic performance and school failure.
2. Anxiety and depression.
3. Sense of guilt.
4. Negative self-concept, low self-esteem and self-loathing.

5. Lack of assertiveness.
6. Terror and panic.
7. Dysthymia (mood disorders, such as sadness) and autolysis (suicidal ideation) Insecurity, behavioral disorders and avoidance behaviors; introversion, shyness, social isolation and loneliness.
8. Low popularity and sometimes unpopularity
9. Low openness to social relationships and low friendliness.
10. Many irrational beliefs (such as astrology and good or bad omens)
11. Low family satisfaction.
12. Low responsibility;
13. Low activity and low efficiency.
14. Low emotional intelligence.
15. Post-traumatic stress syndrome and flashbacks.
16. I refuse to go to school.
17. Anger.
18. Neurotic manifestations.
19. Various somatizations such as insomnia, enuresis and physical pain.
20. Persistence of symptoms in the long term and in adulthood.
21. In more extreme cases, suicide.
22. They usually change schools

Characterizations of the main theoretical construct

Figure 1: School Violence Construction

Source: Own elaboration

The aggressor presents a problem in his attitude, manifesting aggressive behaviors (physical and psychological). For this purpose, several procedures that determine his personality enter into the dynamic, referring both to what determines its occurrence in lexical language (lexical analysis), to what it represents through its behavior or acts (behavioral analysis), to what is obtained as factors after applying the techniques of factorial analysis to questionnaires or qualifications (statistical

analysis), and to the interpretation of the structure of the personality through theoretical buildings (theoretical derivation) (Guzmán 2015; Bausela 2008). With regard to aggression, a fundamental element present in this harassment, which can occur as we have seen previously in various forms, it should be noted that it is processed in the following way, explained as a graph below:

Figure 2: Dimensions influenced by aggression

Source: Own elaboration

The personality of the subject-victim also has a fundamental role in this type of violence, due to the characteristics that he presents in his behaviour, which make him an easy target for the harasser. The main personality trait of the victim is his low self-concept (Adams 2011; Cerezo 2009). The great importance of the social image in the adolescent (in this case) should be emphasized, which is why it is fundamental that the individual has a good self-image and inner strength so that his peers see that he is a valuable and self-confident person (Rodriguez 2014). But fundamentally, this self-concept must be worked on so that the subject is happy with himself, achieving an inner well-being. This will at the same time improve his social skills and his relationship with others (Melero 2017).

Problematic priorities for educational assistance

In the previous section, we explained the different problems that school bullying involves, and now we consider it important to prioritize different aspects so that we can highlight that in a situation of bullying, this is the most immediate thing that we must analyze and act upon, and for this reason, in certain cases, we will not have to deal directly with this problem but rather move pieces of the environment so that it can be resolved more effectively (Capella 2009). We should opt for a systemic perspective and not a static one, since the problem does not lie in the intrapsychic behaviours of the subject but in using all the elements of his environment to change the situation.

Selection of the most relevant variable for one of these priorities

This study focuses on the proposal of a solution that requires the participation of family, colleagues and agents that make up the educational and social environment. As it has been pointed out, the victim is characterized by being a weak person with a low self-concept, who is at a disadvantage with regard to his or her harasser. That is why the variables that should be dealt with should be, as a priority, to treat the personality of the victim, making him/her see that he/she is a person capable of getting out of this situation, that he/she is valuable and that he/she has the inner strength to do so. For all these reasons I consider that one of the most relevant variables that can be empowered to "solve" this situation in a more efficient way is the self-concept.

Diagnostic contrast procedures for the evaluation of this variable in the person of the case

In order to corroborate that the subject presents a problem of self-concept (which makes it difficult for him to have sufficient skills and inner strength to face his situation, since he is inferior to his aggressor, which causes a situation of imbalance from which the bully takes advantage) it is important to use four diagnostic contrast procedures:

1. Interview with the parents: This interview will be semi-structured, and will have the purpose of collecting all the necessary information about the subject/victim. In turn, we will contrast this information with the application of a test on the subject, the ESPA-29 (Montero and Jimenez 2009). Scale of parental socialization styles in adolescence. The main purpose of this test is for the child to assess the performance of his or her father and mother in order to obtain data about them. This information can be valuable to know if the family has any influence on the self-concept of the subject or for other information of interest.

2. Interview with the tutor: This interview will be very useful since the tutor spends many hours throughout the week with his or her students at school and therefore knows information that the family may not recognize and can help us in a decisive way. In this interview it would be very interesting to propose to the tutor the possibility of providing the PRECONCIMEI test (Rubio 2012). Questionnaire on preconceptions of bullying and mistreatment among peers. This test is very powerful to know the impressions concerning the violent behaviour in the school environment by students, parents and teachers.

3. Participant observation

4. Rely on evidence/test such as:

a. AFA. Self-concept Form A: The AFA test is a questionnaire that analyzes the different aspects of the subject's self-concept. Within these aspects we can find the social, academic, emotional and family (Musitu, García, and Gutiérrez 1997).

b. BAS-3. Socialization Battery. This test can be defined as a questionnaire that evaluates different dimensions of social behavior. It also provides a global appreciation of the degree of social adaptation (Silva and Martorell 1984).

c. E.H.S. Social Skills Scale. This test is a very valuable instrument to analyze the person's assertiveness and social skills (Gismero 2002).

d. Sociometric, It is a very powerful and valuable tool that can help us to understand and improve the classroom climate through the sociometric analysis of relationships between equals, such as cohesion, popularity, isolation or group hierarchy, obtaining a socio-affective map of the classroom (Casanova 1991).

Behavioral modification and educational intervention programs for prevention and developmental enhancement

The program designed by Carmen Morán Sánchez (2006) for the elimination of a situation of school bullying in an educational center, presents a cognitive-behavioral perspective, in which it is attempted through a series of techniques and interventions, to modify and enhance the intimate and personal dimension of the bullied student, through therapeutic techniques, as we can see below:

TABLE 4: IMPLICATIONS OF AN EDUCATIONAL INTERVENTION PROGRAM FOR BULLYING

Psychopathological aspects	Therapeutic techniques
Self-esteem deficit	Cognitive restructuring
Anxiety	Diaphragmatic breathing
Assertive deficit	Assertive training
Communication skills deficit	Communication skills training
Problem solving deficits	Training in problem solving
Educational deficit of parents	Self-instructional training

Source: Information adapted from Morán, 2006

The aspects that this program works on have as much to do with the self-esteem that the subject presents, his social skills and the involvement of his parents. In addition, this program carries out an intervention with the different agents that have to do with the school harassment, and that are involved.

TABLE 5: OBJECTIVES AND STRATEGIES OF AN EDUCATIONAL INTERVENTION PROGRAM FOR BULLYING

Objectives	Intervention strategies
With the teachers: 1: Sensitizing teachers to the problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assessment of the situation - Analysis of collected data - Transmission of the results to the teaching staff and the school council - Implementation of the intervention programme - Regular meetings of the teaching staff - Coordination of tutoring
With the students: 1: Sensitizing students to the problem 2: Preventing situations of violence 3: Detecting and controlling school violence	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Interviews with the victim and all the other students - Work on mentoring hours on the expression of violence, personal rights through dramatization of problem situations, role-playing and group discussion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Social skills training - Problem solving training - Weekly individual interviews with students to detect possible situations of violence - Increased surveillance of the playgrounds and common areas
With the family: 1: Sensitize parents to the problem	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Parenting School - Parent meetings

Source: Information adapted from Morán, 2006

The aim is therefore to improve self-esteem, review assertive strategies, strengthen communication and problem-solving skills and advice from the subject's parents.

On the other hand, it is also important to review prevention and improvement programs for this type of situations, since it is the most effective way to obtain a good coexistence in the classroom. For this reason, the following are some intervention programs that have the purpose of making students aware of this type of situation and that acquire the necessary skills both to solve them and to achieve adequate school coexistence (Lavall 2017).

TABLE 6: BULLYING PREVENTION AND IMPROVEMENT PROGRAMS

Preventive Educational Intervention and Developmental Enhancement Programs
<p>1. Why try - A program used with individuals and/or groups that teaches good decision-making skills. The program uses visual analogies that are easy to remember. Students learn that decisions have consequences for them as well as others</p> <p>2. Character counts - By following the 6 pillars of character: trust, respect, responsibility, fairness, understanding and citizenship, students learn to treat each other with dignity and respect</p> <p>3. "Think Twice, Be Kind" - A presentation offered by the Women's Center to teach children about respect and how to treat others in a polite manner</p> <p>4. Kelso's Choice - Learning Conflict Management Skills is the goal of this program. When students have differences, it teaches them how to resolve those differences in a friendly and respectful way</p> <p>5. Let's take violence seriously - This program redirects bullying and teasing and helps build a culture of acceptance and non-violence. Lessons include videos and discussions</p> <p>6. Stop, Think, Act, Review (S.T.A.R.) - Teaches personal responsibility through a four-step process in which the student learns to think before adopting a bullying behavior</p> <p>7. Don't Laugh at Me - This is a program based on the song "Don't Laugh at Me" and teaches students how to create a respectful, safe and supportive environment.</p> <p>8. Bullies never win - In this program, students are offered scenarios of bullying and strategies for dealing with those situations</p>

Source: Own elaboration

II. CONCLUSION

The purpose of the study we carried out was to identify and highlight the aspects that revolve around the problem known as "bullying", especially those who are ignorant or unaware of the subject, be it parents, teachers or even the students themselves. It leaves us with many important things to think about and many others it has reinforced such as being able to identify an aggressor or a victim through observation, without the need to apply psychoanalysis.

Among the points that we consider most important in a project of this nature are detecting attitudes, postures, motor forms of expression, language, gestures, among others to identify what role the child takes in a situation of school bullying, as it is easier to take action to solve the issue or less control it, on the other hand define clearly and as tangibly as possible why someone is likely to be part of the problem, based on the environment in which it develops and the people with whom they live.

Information is one of the most important resources that children have to form their minds and the fact that schools do not take initiative to control the problem, or rather eliminate it, is a factor that encourages bullying. Children need to know their rights and also their limitations. School authorities should be more selective in hiring their teachers, and in our opinion, know at least the basics about the problem we have raised. Finally, it is important that they have a counsellor who listens to them (in case their parents do not), who feels supported and does not perceive isolation as a means of escape.

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